

Curricula Of Islamic Seminaries Of Pakistan: Critical Overview And Way Forward

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 17, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 21, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Madaris, Curricula, Problems, Contemporary Issues, Reforms</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5590972</p>	<p><i>Curriculum contrary to syllabus is a vast term that includes teaching methods, lessons, class activities, assignments, physical and mental exercises, projects, study material, presentation etc. Curriculum of any institute builds the mental personality of a student which takes part in the development of a society according to the contents a student bears during his study. In Pakistani society, madaris have a vital role in the development of Islamic learning. On the other hand science and scientific method is a big challenge for madaris curricula as it is the era of science and scientific method which is being rejected by madaris with some exemptions. The contents of the madaris curricula are most challengeable in contemporary times. Owing to everyday changes in the world of God, one may precept that there should be changing in the curriculum of our Islamic learning process which may lead us to the true spirit of Islam that is recognition of Almighty Allah. Most of the studies with the title of Curricula in the context of Pakistani madaris evolve around the one part of the curriculum whereas the problems of Madaris not only because of their syllabus but because of the problems in their curriculum as well that is the whole system of madaris education. Do the Pakistani Seminaries (madaris) work on the curricula? How much these curricula are outdated? What are the gaps in their curricula? This study is an analytical evaluation of this topic with outcomes and suitable suggestions.</i></p>

Introduction

Curriculum in general understanding of public is subject matter or a series of written materials like books and syllabi but educationists took up this term in broad sense referring to: the totality of student experiences that occur in the educational process. In other words: the curriculum represents a set of desired goals or values that are activated through a development process and culminate in successful learning experiences for students.

Being an Islamic ideology-based country, it was essential for Pakistan to ensure that its education system and curriculum would be formed on true Islamic ideology in both-religious and so called secular- sort of prevailing systems of education that leads both to unified form of knowledge as there is no concept of duality-religious(*deeni*) and secular(worldly/*dunyawi*) -within knowledge and instead education systems are thought of in terms of beneficial(*nafi*) and harmful(*darr*) knowledge. Keeping this in mind, it is obvious that both systems need to be reformed and reconstructed. But this study is going to be carried out pertaining to the problems of curricula of Pakistani madaris, so the focus would be solely on madaris curricula. There are many problems regarding the curricula of Pakistani madaris those lie in their objectives, teaching methodology, teaching style, syllabus, research and evaluation. Prof. Khursheed opined that our religious education system has not been accessible and effective to meet the challenge of present civilization. It can no doubt create a religious leadership that is a great service in its place but those who will be access it will meet the challenge of modern civilization, are not only present but are not being prepared.

Significance of Research

Curriculum of any education system is a parameter for the development of personalities and abilities of the individuals to meet the upcoming challenges. According to Abul Hasan Ali Nadvi, it is a widely accepted and well known fact that curriculum has an important and vital role in the mental construction of new generation, creation of leadership quality and to get benefits from the previous branches of knowledge and books*. Since the study consists curricula of Pakistani madaris.

Research Problem

The basic question that is being addressed and analyzed within this research pertains to the development of curricula for madaris in Pakistan which is in line with the current times. It has become evident that there is a gap

within what Islam intended for in terms of education and what is actually being taught to students through the current curricula. These challenges are further exacerbated by the decline of education regarding Western philosophies and their relation to Islamic ideology. Most modern scholars have rejected any link between Western philosophies and teachings of Islam which prevents the curricula from becoming broader and prevents students from attaining knowledge about all aspects of the world. Thus, this research attempts to analyze this topic as well as provide recommendations and solutions to address this issue appropriately.

Study Framework

In order to conduct this study appropriately, both futuristic and historic approaches are integrated and utilized. The main purpose of using the historic research approach was to study, interpret and understand the past events in relation to the topic as this could provide relevant conclusions or insights about the development of curricula in the past as well as what purpose education serves in Islam. In regards to the futuristic approach, there was a need to systematically analyze the circumstances and events of the future in order to provide recommendations that could be useful in the development of an appropriate and educated curricula for madaris in Pakistan. In order to critically analyze the topic, various secondary and primary sources were used which aided in the establishment of in-depth comprehension regarding the Islamic ideology-based education system as well as its relation with education systems in the West. In Islam, it is believed that Quran provides the best understanding and education of the world as it informs individuals about Allah and His various creations. Furthermore, Quran as well as ahadis have also informed Muslims regarding the importance of education as this is a means of growing close to Allah by learning about not only Islamic matters alone but also other broader and general topics as well. For instance, in past education systems, philosophy and various other fields were also considered to be crucial for the strong mental development of individuals but these have continually been replaced with an Islam-specific curricula which is not as well-informed given the lack of understanding and awareness about Islam itself. After this analysis with the historic approach, the futuristic approach aids in looking ahead and putting forward some useful solutions and recommendations that could allow the government as well as madaris in Pakistan to develop a curricula that is aligned with the contemporary times instead of being out of touch with reality and leading people far away from the Ultimate Reality.

Research Questions

1. Are Pakistani seminaries or madaris making any preparations for their curricula?
2. To what extent are the current curricula of madaris outdated?
3. What gaps exist within the current curricula of madaris?
4. What significance has been given to the Western philosophies and education and does it have any contribution within existing curricula?

Literature Review

1. Khalid Rahman, A.D. Mekan, *Pakistan mein deeni ta'leem, manzar, pas i manzar o pesh i manzar*, Institute of policy study, Islamabad, 2009: comprising of 367 pages. This book provides the details about government's role and national policy regarding religious study, curriculum and teaching methodology, religious study and the standard of research and journalism, discussion about reforms, conclusion and recommendation.
2. Saleem Mansoor Khalid, *deeni madaris mein taleem:kefiyyat, masail, and imkanat*, Institute of policy study, Islamabad, 2002: comprising 467 pages. This book is a detailed research study about Pakistani madaris. Besides introduction and entreaties, the book contains lectures of some of the renowned Pakistani scholars regarding religious institutions, background of Islamic learning in subcontinent, Pakistani religious madaris and their prevailing situation as well as problems pertaining to teaching methods, syllabi, and students along with their solutions. The book is compiled with references of great scholars. It is in fact a particular guideline for the administrator Ulema of Pakistani madaris. Since the study encompasses the matter until 2002, further research needs to find out how much changes have occurred in Pakistani madaris during the last seventeen years.
3. Dr. M. Ameen, *hamara deeni nizam i ta'leem*, Lahore: darul ikhlas, 2008. This is another remarkable work that can aid in finding out the problems about madaris and their solutions. A part of the book comprises of dialogue between the ulema of diverse backgrounds. There are many useful and accessible solution suggested in the matter. The book has 314 pages.

Articles:

1. Junaid Ahmad Hashimi, Haroon ur Rasheed, *Al-manahij fi dirasat i aldeen bain al-tayyarat i ma'rafiyyat al-islamiyyah fi bakistan, ma laha wa ma alaiha*: Lahore: al-adhwa 29:42, pp: 303-314. This study provides background, origin and methodologies adopted by Pakistani madaris of different sects. A critical analysis has been conducted of the topic and some modern contents have been suggested in addition to ongoing syllabus of *dars i nizami*.
2. Niaz Muhammad and co., *Madaris of Pakistan and Challenges of Modern World*, (Dera Ismail Khan: Gomal University Journal of Research, 28(2) December, 2012). Pp.39-51.

3. Muhammad Ammar Khan Nasir, *Deeni Madaris ka murawwaja nisab: aik mukhtasar jaiza*: This article emphasizes on criticism regarding syllabus of madaris. The author took up specific points of criticism on the Holy Quran, Hadith, Fiqh, Arabic literature, logic and philosophy. Comparing between the syllabus of Wafaqul Madaris and wafaqul madaris Salafiyah, he put forward some important changes in this connection.
4. Muhammad Kashif Sheikh, *Pakistan ky Deeni Madaris ky Nisab ka Mutala' Ma'arif Majall i Tahqeeq*, July to December, 2017, pp. 35-60: The article sheds light on the prophetic method of teaching and syllabus, thus raising questions about the madaris syllabus. Despite the general title of the article, syllabus of Pakistani *madaris* linked to the biography of Prophet (PBUH) has also been discussed. And there are many other studies, books and articles pertaining to the topic with different dimensions.

Elements of Curriculum

Curriculum comprises four basic elements which are as follows:

1. Objectives and Aims
2. Contents
3. Teaching and learning experiences
4. Evaluation.

In fact, curriculum is not a group of these four elements and instead is referred to as interlink of these elements.

1. Objectives and Aims of Curriculum

Objectives and aims are basic elements for curriculum of any education system. Looking back to the history of Curriculum of *madaris*, the objectives and aims were followed by a philosophy which was to serve the religion and to seek knowledge under the shadow of religion that resulted in the consideration of education as a religious obligation and not just a worldly matter in one's life. Muslim scholars established a constructive and suitable curriculum based on the true Islamic thoughts. They included ancient philosophy (philosophy of Aristotle and Plato), Astronomy, Mathematics, Geography, History, but all these were under the fold of Islamic shade. It is rightly said by Dr. Waheed Quraishi that the education is one destination to gain access to the Ultimate Reality and objective of education can only be determined through this fundamental reality. In addition to that, since the socio-economic needs were also in the top objectives of education, there was a need for the inclusion of the study of medicine along with other natural sciences to meet any financial challenges. As curriculum is founded on the basis of Islamic ideology, there should be a unanimous national policy which would cover all our institutions and their functions including the educational institutes. Unfortunately, after seventy years, we have still been unable to agree on one national agenda. But now objectives and aims are lacking which is why Pakistani madaris have decided their curriculum in a random manner. Dr. Rafiuddin pointed out that the cause behind this randomness which is present within all spheres of life is that we are unable to comprehend what should be the political, economic, educational, legal or preaching system in Islam. In fact, when we are not well-acquainted with Islam and our knowledge about it is limited, then it is quite impossible to determine what Islam wants to achieve. According to him, modern Western philosophies and Muslims dealing with them in terms of absolute rejection is a main factor of decline.

Islam-ideology Based Syllabus/content

It is claimed that the Holy Quran and Hadith are the primary and fundamental place in Pakistani Islamic learning institutes and other sciences as well as arts are considered to be tools that support the understanding of these two basic sources. But many *ulema* who have been teaching *Dars i nizami* declared their observations on this matter. According to Sayyid Abul Ala Maududi, Islamic sciences should not be taken as ancient books as they are; instead, the focus should be on deriving eternal and unchangeable principles and beliefs of Islam from them by avoiding the mixing it with modern times. Then, this needs to be poured in student's heart so that their spirits may become pure and right understanding can be developed within their minds. There is no such thing as a ready-made syllabus to achieve this particular goal which means everything needs to be reconstructed. The Holy Quran and Hadith are prerequisite overall but not from the old exegetical and hadith. It is the same case with other sciences like jurisprudence, History and philosophy of History, Islamic economic, etc. All of these sciences and arts should be studied under Islamic framework. Dr. Mehmood Ahmad Ghazi (2012) opined that prevailing specialization in exegetic within many madaris is just cursory and depthless study of the Holy Quran. It only produces scholars who are able to deliver Quranic lessons to public or eristically. However, they remain unacquainted with the Quranic sciences, exegeses, methodology of exegetics, history of compilation of the Holy Quran, and the doubts as well as objections raised in modern era.

It is suggested that the syllabus be improved in accordance with the current times. In ongoing syllabus of Dars e Nizami, English Language, History, Geography, Mathematics, Computer, Economics, Political Science need to be added. Ancient Philosophy and Logic are suggested to be replaced with Research; however, ancient philosophy and Logic should be replaced with modern Philosophy and Logic along with modern Western thoughts from which modernism, postmodernism and other scientific approaches have been derived. Modern Western thoughts regarding natural sciences and materialistic approaches are major challenges to religious

thoughts which means that these need to be studied within Pakistani madaris so that these challenges could be addressed.

Teaching and Learning Experience

Prophetic way of Teaching: Prophet Muhammad (Peace & Blessing of Allah be on Him) was sent as a teacher (Muallim) and along with this He (PBUH) was kind to all worlds. He implemented the question and answer method along with demonstration.

Teaching style: Teaching is an indispensable part of learning process. Effective teaching results in a productive and constructive society in future. Authoritarian, indifferent and laissez-faire are different styles of teaching implemented in education. In madaris, teacher is generally an authoritarian one whereas some may be indifferent. Owing to teachers' authoritarian attitude, students sometimes are unable to even interact and communicate with them. In the case of indifferent teachers, it only results in students simply becoming passive listeners and have zero communication with their teachers. Thus, the teachers are only focused on solving complicated texts from outdated books and the students are largely ignored. Such a situation can become even worse when the number of students is particularly large. Furthermore, students are often discouraged from having verbal discussions and exchanges amongst one another or with the teachers. In such a situation, the students are being prevented from improving their communication skills through learning and/or practice as well.

Text Centered learning: In early and medieval period of Muslim education system, students were a central component of education which later on was adopted into the modern education system as well; however, madaris education mainly revolves around the texts and books. In student-centered education, student is given complete and full attention and every student is given proper consideration by the teacher until the fulfillment of the goals of the curriculum. On the other hand, the focus in madrasa education is all on the solution of complicated, hard and outdated books. Students only end up becoming passive listeners since they are given no attention or care by teachers which results in failure within life as well as failure of the curriculum itself. In October 1994, a seminar was held in Darul Uloom Deoband where it was declared that in madrasa education priority should be given to the method of teaching instead of focusing on syllabus.

According to Sayyid Abul A'la Maududi, there is a reason for teaching prophetic tradition (*Hadith*) in madaris: the teachings of Hadith which are required for a *Muhadith* (expert in *Hadith*) cannot be found anywhere. Traditional method of teaching hadith is as follows: while teaching hadith related to jurisprudential or theological dispute, a few days are spent on it. On the other hand, hadith related to the reality of religion or those bearing narration of economic, political, social and ethical system of Islam or those which shed light on constitution of country, judicial system or international relationships require both the teacher and pupil to go through everything carefully to fully grasp it.

Co-curricular and Extracurricular Activities

It is noteworthy that co-curricular and extra-curricular activities were part of the prophetic curriculum. If poetry and elocution were among co-curricular activities during the Prophetic period, horse and camel riding, swimming, archery, running, swordplay and wrestling were extra-curricular activities. Hence, both activities can be adopted according to the suitability and needs of current times. And Prophet Muhammad (Peace & Blessing be on Him) said:

"عن أبي هريرة رضي الله عنه قال: قال رسول الله صلى الله عليه وسلم: المؤمن القوي خير وأحب إلى الله من المؤمن الضعيف وفي كل خير. احرص على ما ينفعك"

(Abu Hurairah (R.A) reported Messenger of Allah (PBUH) said: A strong believer is better and dearer to Allah than a weak one, and both are good. Adhere to that which is beneficial for you).

Co-curricular activities create and uncover concealed abilities of students and play a vital role in enhancing their personalities. It is another means of communication and cooperation amongst the students of different institutions and it can serve as the bridge between students with different sectarian thoughts. Furthermore, it can establish harmony within society as well. Unfortunately, *madaris* have no such plans and mechanisms in place within their education systems; rather, such activities are highly discouraged lest the students deviate from their studies. This is the reason as to why personalities of students cannot be developed with the true spirit of Islam. Currently, the gap between students of one madaris and others is only becoming worse.

Evaluation of Curriculum

Evaluation of curriculum is another integral part of overall education system which needs to be considered in accordance with the changes occurring within different spheres of human life. Curriculum evaluation should not be misinterpreted as student evaluation. In case of *madaris* syllabus or content of learning, it might not be applicable within the knowledge that is based on revelation like in the *Holy Quran* and *Hadith*; however, this can be applicable within their interpretation and content related to other sciences. Evaluation of teaching and learning experiences along with achievement of aims and objectives is also necessary with the passage of time. *Madaris* have not been taken into any consideration by the government regarding their curricula. Although the evaluation is a dynamic process, the organizers of these *madaris* have not paid any attention towards it.

Madaris and Research

Except for the research during last year by dars i nizami, most madaris have no remarkable research activity. This is due to the fact that the syllabus of madaris does not have material on research methodology. Research activities are not encouraged during study. In addition to this, lack of research resources like libraries, computers etc. is quite a common issue in most of Pakistani madaris. It is affable and encouraging that research studies were initiated within madaris during the last few years; comparisons can even be made between the topics that were researched in 2003 and those in 2019. The features of research carried out in madaris include: repetition of the researched topics, work on personalities instead of on sources of Shari'ah, subjectivity and biasness within sects, narrow perspective, absence of research study on topics like economics, politics, social issues, comparative religions and challenges pertaining to Islam and Muslims, and use of complicated Arabic phrases.

Madaris and Challenge of Contemporary World

Modern philosophical and scientific thoughts are major challenges for the Muslim world now. Contemporary and modern human trends are based on two things (i) mind/logic (ii) worldly benefits. This means that nobody will accept religion or religious approach without having the abovementioned trends regardless of whether they are right or wrong. Dr. Rafiuddin opined that the decline of Islam are due to those Western philosophical thoughts whose influence has spread all around the world. Both our intellectuals and non-intellectuals are affected by such thoughts. According to him, visionaries do not result in inertia and stillness of Islam but they are a sign of inertia and stillness. We can get rid of this stillness by considering gold and modern scientific (Physics, Biology, Psychology) and philosophical facts which are appropriate to the spirit of the Holy Qura'n as Quranic facts. This is by the virtue of the ayah of the Holy Qura'n:

(سَنُرِيهِمْ آيَاتِنَا فِي الْأَفَاقِ وَفِي أَنْفُسِهِمْ حَتَّىٰ يَتَبَيَّنَ لَهُمْ أَنَّهُ الْحَقُّ أَوَلَمْ يَكْفِ بِرَبِّكَ أَنَّهُ عَلَىٰ كُلِّ شَيْءٍ شَهِيدٌ)

(We will show them Our Signs in the universe and in their own selves, until it becomes manifest to them that this (the Quran) is the truth. Is it not sufficient in regard to your lord that he is a Witness over all things?)

Conclusion

The study concludes:

1. Pakistani Islamic Seminaries do contribute to the Islamic Sciences without a doubt.
2. In term of curriculum, there are no specific objectives being defined for the education provided in these seminaries.
3. Scientific teaching techniques are not being adopted by teachers in seminaries.
4. Education is mainly books and text-oriented.
5. Teachers' behaviors are authoritarian most of the times and indifferent at other times which results in many physiological and linguistic problems for students.
6. Problem in syllabus causes a weak foundation to be built within students regarding the basic and primary sources of Islam (Holy Quran and Sunnah) along with other contemporary sciences and arts.
7. The problem of sectarianism, research activities, and to meet modern philosophical and scientific challenges are still addressed in old canvas.
8. There is a dire need for attention from government as well as from administration of these seminaries; so that they may become aware of these problems and then try their best to eliminate them so that a constructive ideological foundation can be built.

Recommendation

It is recommended that:

1. Clergy of Pakistan realize these problems first and then should agree to take some positive steps to eradicate them.
2. They should not feel insecure while addressing these issues as that would be for the sake and betterment of Muslims, Islam and their own selves.
3. Government should provide financial and logistic support particularly in the case of launching natural sciences in the seminaries of the country.
4. Seminaries should adopt modern techniques to set their objectives for holistic education as well as the syllabus of each subject for effective outcomes.
5. Positive teaching behaviors and styles should be implemented keeping in view the diversity amongst students.

Education should be student-centered and every student should be paid proper attention. This would require logistic support of the government. Thus, the role of government needs to be significant in bringing about positive changes.

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 (رَبَّنَا آتِنَا فِي الدُّنْيَا حَسَنَةً وَفِي الْآخِرَةِ حَسَنَةً وَقِنَا عَذَابَ النَّارِ) Surah Al-Baqarah, 2: 201 (our lord! Give us in this world that which is good and in the hereafter that which is good and save us from the torment of the Fire!). And

- Prophet Muhammad (peace & blessing be on Him) said (أُخْرِصْ عَلَى مَا يَنْفَعُكَ): adhere to that which is beneficial for you). (Muslim bin Hajjaj (261 AH) Sahih Muslim, Chapter: 46, Hadith: 2664. In another Hadith Prophet Muhammad (peace & blessing of Allah be on Him)'s supplication narrated from Jabir (R.A) (سَلُوا اللَّهَ عِلْمًا نَافِعًا ، وَتَعَوَّذُوا بِاللَّهِ مِنْ عِلْمٍ لَا يَنْفَعُ) (Ask Allah for beneficial knowledge and seek refuge with Allah from knowledge). Ibn e Majjah, Sunan Ibn e Majjah, Book: 34, Hadith: 17.
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